

STUDY OF THE RELATIVE ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF A DRUM MILL TYPE SAG 8.5 X 5.3

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ABSTRACT. The article discusses the topic of the specific power consumption of a drum mill type SAG 8.5x5.3. The purpose of the study is to determine the influence of some basic parameters like angular velocity of the mill drum, the wear on the drum's lining, mass of the mill filling, loading rate of the mill with ore and flow rate of incoming water of the product to be milled on the relative power consumption of the mill for maintaining quality. To determine the energy consumption of the mill, the listed parameters were measured and a Fisher matrix was constructed. In accordance with the selected target function, energy consumption patterns are synthesised depending on the loading rate of the mill with ore, the mass of the mill filling, the flow rate of the incoming water and the wear on the drum's lining. Data processing was performed using the STATGRAPHICS computer programme and an adequate model has been found according to the selected target function. The target function has been found to satisfy the conditions for maintaining quality and reducing costs.

Keywords: drum mill, relative power consumption, mass of the mill filling, loading rate

Introduction

One of the main goals in modern production is to reduce harmful emissions, reduce production costs, and improve quality of production or energy use (Utu et al., 2018; Nyandwe et al., 2020). It is not always possible to achieve these goals simultaneously. Given the high cost of electricity and the generated harmful emissions during its production, it is appropriate for the main target function in energy-intensive industries to reduce energy consumption while maintaining the quality of production. Such industries are the crushing and milling of ore in the mining industry. It is known that the high quality of the product of these two processes leads to lower prices and higher product quality in the next process - flotation (Boteva et al., 2003). Therefore, the purpose of the present study is to determine a minimum power consumption model for a SAG 8.5x5.3 drum mill.

Choice of control parameters and target function

Clearly formulating the purpose of the study is a fundamental and important step in determining the target function. A poorly worded goal leads to inefficient control of the object. Of course, when the goal changes, the target function must change, and hence the research.

The choice of a target function is the most important task in modelling objects, and it is allowed to apply the methods of mathematical statistics. In this case, the object is a mill. This is a multifactorial object with nonlinear influence of the parameters relative to each other.

The first task in the modelling of drum semi-autogenous mills (SAG Mills) is the clear formulation of the goal. Given the weak data on the subject of the study and the high complexity of the object (mill), it is clear that this step is one of the most difficult and at the same time one of the most responsible. The aim, when formulated incorrectly, makes the research meaningless or at least incomplete. Obviously, in order to achieve this goal, first of all, it is necessary to characterise it clearly and strictly

The choice of a target function, allowing the application of the methods of mathematical statistics is a step in the process

of modelling (Bojanov et al., 1973; Bojanov et al., 1979). For this reason, the target function is formulated according to some certain requirements.

A properly formulated target function is characterised by quantity, i.e. each combination of values of the input factors to be characterised by a number. The set of values that the target function can accept is called the domain of its definition. This area can be definite or indefinite, continuous or discrete. The target function needs to be measurable in order to be set. The target function must be unitary.

In many cases, this requirement is met automatically because the goal is set strictly and its characteristic is one. The most common functions of this type are economic goals (costs, energy consumption, etc.) (Nikolov and Nikolova, 2006).

The target function must be effective, i.e. to effectively characterise the work of SAG Mills in accordance with the set goal. In addition, the efficiency of the target function does not remain constant in the process of research and optimisation. For example, when organising production in the initial stage, the most effective target function is the volume of production. When the final opportunities for increasing production are reached, the role of other parameters such as quality, production cost, etc. acquire significance. Therefore, once the target function is selected, it will not be considered an invariant parameter. At some point in the study, it may need to be replaced with another, more effective, target function.

The requirement for efficiency is also directly related to the requirement for completeness of the target function. This means that the target function must characterise extensively and fully the desired objective. The target function must also be statistically effective, i.e. with the minimum possible variance 2. In practice, this requirement is limited to the choice of a target function that can be measured (calculated with the greatest possible accuracy).

In the present study, the energy efficiency per unit of product - E, kWh/t - the amount of electricity consumption per unit of production was chosen as a target function (Hristova et al., 2018; Istalianov and Lakov, 2019).

Of course, other target functions can be accepted, such as the wear of the drum linings per tonne of milled product with

parameters such as change in the trajectory of the particles (Stoyanov, 2015), humidity, hardness and others. These target functions may be more noticeable after describing the most significant and specific phenomena in the process of milling materials in SAG mills.

It can be said that the chosen target function meets the condition of efficiency, has a clear physical meaning and has a quantitative characteristic - for each set of values of its factors an exact number of its defining region can be assigned. As a starting parameter, energy consumption is also statistically efficient, as the value can be accurately measured.

Energy consumption is a parameter that characterises the process in quantitative terms and this determines its main disadvantage - it is not the only one (Nikolova and Nikolov, 2006).

Results from the experiment

In a previous study (Hristova, 2015) the independent influence of factors such as the amount of the processed ore, the mill speed, the filling with water and ore on energy consumption was analysed. The parameters - the quantity of ore and water are basic for the quality of the milled product in the semi-autogenous mills and for this reason their joint influence on the relative specific consumption of electricity has been studied. To obtain a real picture of energy consumption as a target function, it is necessary to include more input parameters - motor power P , kW; motor speed n , min^{-1} ; amount of water Q_w , m^3/h ; amount of ore Q , t; mass of filling M , t; yield of the estimated class of the final product K ,%. The specified parameters were measured during the operation of a real object drum mill type SAG 8.5x5.3. The values of the measured parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Table with data for measured parameters

No	Processing t	P kW	n min^{-1}	Q_w m^3/h	Q t/h	M T	K %
1	552564	5852,1	1062,6	14,3	233	107,3	81,43
2	664145	5773,6	1067,2	19,86	135	103,5	75,7
3	744820	5960,2	1087,6	44,86	258,4	99,33	78,66
4	849393	6105	1092,3	35,85	189,97	93,3	80,42
5	2400	5014	1060,2	25,25	238,4	110,5	74,96
6	98219	5324,2	1004,3	29,53	207,3	114,2	78,34
7	214304	4900	989,3	80,7	248,44	109,33	79,38
8	291695	5306,7	1013,5	72,36	188,7	108,9	80,34
9	347273	5252,5	1017,3	30	200,8	80,35	80,25
10	429549	5478,6	1016,7	40	180,8	106,3	81,2
11	562018	5353,4	1014	75,3	221,3	96,4	79
12	706758	5500,8	1118,1	80,25	243,45	90,4	78,73
13	577	4727,5	1001,6	65,1	245	112,9	81,2
14	165820	5277,9	991,6	94,2	252,33	113,1	82,2
15	315588	2979,7	873,5	35	234	102,7	78,5
16	414322	5431	1000,2	88,2	241,8	113	78,5
17	544572	5544,6	1035,6	74,9	260,1	107,7	78,8
18	695262	5459,2	1035,8	93,6	248,9	102,1	81,22
19	3619	4570,1	1001,2	54,6	274,3	118,1	77,64
20	110596	4588,7	980,83	60	260	115,8	75,4
21	182173	3325	876,66	50	250,9	110	76,8
22	262135	4630	968,56	70,8	276,1	113,7	75,8
23	376682	4612,2	956,8	88,5	251,5	111,76	74,57
24	490079	5249	1015,3	169	315,13	110,44	77
25	624588	5350,7	1051,9	171	334,77	106,5	76,98
26	700629	5289,5	1058,9	170,47	318,92	106,76	75,56
27	750266	5217,1	1078,6	206,6	288,1	99,73	75,5
28	855959	5278,3	1092,1	185,5	318,14	92,3	76,97
29	0	3825	894,54	160,9	281,2	112,9	79,11
30	113137	4591,4	941,96	249,6	322,41	112,85	75,87
31	228595	4605,3	1003,2	265,1	341,39	112,4	76,55
32	361339	4976,3	1005,3	260	311,1	114,87	76,55
33	434759	5016	1002,1	179,7	315,2	110,4	87,9
34	592296	5146,5	1033,9	180,4	336,7	104,5	87,9
35	670662	5167,5	1036,2	245	298,6	102,1	77,1

Statistical survey of the results of the passive experiment of a drum mill type SAG 8.5 x 5.3

The investigated target function is the relative energy consumption E , kWh/t, which is a result of the ratio of the power of the mill motor measured by the sensors and the productivity of the mill for the final product per unit time.

The relative energy consumption is obtained by the formula:

$$E = \frac{P}{Q}, kWh/t, \quad (1)$$

where:

P , kWh/h – the power, consumed by the drum motor;
 Q , t/h – the productivity of the drum mill.

The relative productivity of the mill is calculated according to the following formula:

$$Q_1 = Q \cdot K, t/h, \quad (2)$$

where:

Q , t/h – in practice is the loading rate of the mill with ore. This parameter is measured by an electronic balance placed on the feed belt of the mill; (Dzhustrov, 2019).

K , % – the yield of the estimated class of the final product, – the ratio of the class – 0,08 to the total quantity processed by the mill drum. It is obtained after a sieve analysis of the obtained material at the outlet of the mill.

The measurement results obtained are given in Table 2. In this table the treatment of the mill (from the moment of laying new drum linings to the moment of measurement) is represented by the percentage of the wear of the lining.

In this situation 0% corresponds to a new lining and 100% to a completely worn lining.

The data processing in Table 2 is performed by statistical analysis. The whole matrix for the relative energy consumption is processed.

Various methods, algorithms, mathematical apparatus (Mryankov, 2007), machine algorithm for calculation, neural networks are used to achieve the optimal parameters of the surveyed objects. In this case the results of the experiment is appropriate to be statistically processed using the

STATGRAPHICS programme. The results of the statistical analysis of the relative energy consumption are shown in Table 3.

The evaluation of the significance of the regression coefficients is performed according to the Student's criterion (t-criterion) at a significance level $\alpha = 0,05$ and at least 8 degrees of freedom (Df). The programme evaluates the probability of significance of the regression coefficients, i.e. whether they fall within the confidence interval. If this probability is:

$$P - Value < \alpha, \quad (3)$$

so the coefficient of regression is significant (α – confidence probability).

Similarly, the adequacy of the equation is assessed by the significance of the Fisher test (F-Ratio).

For the purposes of the practical study of the operational process, models and regressions are sought, which can be assumed with probability levels of 95% and it is expected that acceptable engineering errors of 5% will be acceptable for technical devices, such as drum -autogenic mills - type SAG 8.5x5.3.

Given the parameters of this model (Table 3), it is obvious that the multiple correlation coefficient R^2 is 98,28% and the corrected multiple correlation coefficient R^2 (adj) is over 98%.

The value of the reliability probability indicator (P-criterion) for the model is below the critical one, i.e. it can be assumed that the model is adequate. The degrees of freedom are 35 and are well above the required 8.

Therefore, the equation of the model describing the relative energy consumption with the natural variables will be:

$$E = 73,753 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot i - 87,6392 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot Q + 0,327158 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot n \cdot M, kWh/t \quad (4)$$

The correspondence between the model values and the experimental data is shown in the comparative diagram in Figure 1.

In the present study, when processing the data, the parameter amount of water Q_w , t/h did not correlate with the other parameters and therefore it is not included in the model.

Table 2. Achieved measurement results

№	i	P	n	Q_w	Q	M	$K_{-0,08}$	E
	%	kW	min ⁻¹	m ³ /h	t/h	T	%	kWh/t
	X1		X2	X3	X4	X5		Y
1	64,555	5852,1	1062,6	14,3	233	107,3	81,43	20,45
2	77,591	5773,6	1067,2	19,86	135	103,5	75,7	32,37
3	87,016	5960,2	1087,6	44,86	258,4	99,33	78,66	18,14
4	99,233	6105	1092,3	35,85	189,97	93,3	80,42	25,84
5	0,280	5014	1060,2	25,25	238,4	110,5	74,96	15,77
6	11,475	5324,2	1004,3	29,53	207,3	114,2	78,34	20,12
7	25,037	4900	989,3	80,7	248,44	109,33	79,38	15,66
8	34,078	5306,7	1013,5	72,36	188,7	108,9	80,34	22,59
9	40,571	5252,5	1017,3	30	200,8	80,35	80,25	20,99
10	50,183	5478,6	1016,7	40	180,8	106,3	81,2	24,61
11	65,659	5353,4	1014	75,3	221,3	96,4	79	19,11
12	82,569	5500,8	1118,1	80,25	243,45	90,4	78,73	17,79
13	0,067	4727,5	1001,6	65,1	245	112,9	81,2	15,67
14	19,372	5277,9	991,6	94,2	252,33	113,1	82,2	17,19

15	36,870	2979,7	873,5	35	234	102,7	78,5	10,00
16	48,404	5431	1000,2	88,2	241,8	113	78,5	17,63
17	63,621	5544,6	1035,6	74,9	260,1	107,7	78,8	16,80
18	81,226	5459,2	1035,8	93,6	248,9	102,1	81,22	17,81
19	0,423	4570,1	1001,2	54,6	274,3	118,1	77,64	12,94
20	12,921	4588,7	980,83	60	260	115,8	75,4	13,31
21	21,283	3325	876,66	50	250,9	110	76,8	10,18
22	30,625	4630	968,56	70,8	276,1	113,7	75,8	12,71
23	44,007	4612,2	956,8	88,5	251,5	111,76	74,57	13,68
24	57,255	5249	1015,3	169	315,13	110,44	77	12,83
25	72,969	5350,7	1051,9	171	334,77	106,5	76,98	12,30
26	81,853	5289,5	1058,9	170,47	318,92	106,76	75,56	12,53
27	87,652	5217,1	1078,6	206,6	288,1	99,73	75,5	13,67
28	100,000	5278,3	1092,1	185,5	318,14	92,3	76,97	12,77
29	0,000	3825	894,54	160,9	281,2	112,9	79,11	10,76
30	13,218	4591,4	941,96	249,6	322,41	112,85	75,87	10,80
31	26,706	4605,3	1003,2	265,1	341,39	112,4	76,55	10,33
32	42,215	4976,3	1005,3	260	311,1	114,87	76,55	12,24
33	50,792	5016	1002,1	179,7	315,2	110,4	87,9	13,99
34	69,197	5146,5	1033,9	180,4	336,7	104,5	87,9	13,44
35	78,352	5167,5	1036,2	245	298,6	102,1	77,1	13,34

Table 3. Parameters of the most adequate model

Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic		P-Value
X ₁	0,073753	0,0126204	5,84394		0,0000
X ₄	-0,0876392	0,00810805	-10,8089		0,0000
X ₂ .X ₅	0,000327158	0,0000200047	16,3541		0,0000
Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	9645,5	3	3215,17	610,39	0,0000
Residue	168,558	32	5,26742		
Total	9814,06	35			
R ² =0				98,2825%	
R ² (adjusted for d.f.) =				98,1751%	
Standard Error of Est. =				2,29509	
Mean absolute error =				1,61305	
Durbin-Watson statistic =				1,44291	
Lag 1 residual autocorrelation =				0,272021	

Figure 1. A comparative chart of the relative energy consumption

Conclusions from the obtained experimental results

The results of the measurements and the statistical analysis of relative energy consumption show the following:

- the relative energy consumption is influenced to the greatest extent by four parameters, namely: the wear of the drum lining, the speed of the drum of the mill, the filling mass and the rate of loading of the ore into the mill;
- this study did not confirm the effect of the amount of water on energy consumption. The reason is the complex influence of a large number of other factors;
- with the increase of the wear of the milling drum lining increases the relative energy consumption of the mill, most likely due to the fact that the larger drum volume increases the relative speed of the drum. This increases the power to raise balls and large pieces of ore;
- the increase in drum speed also leads to an increase in power consumption - a well-known law of physics which confirms the result of the previous study;
- the rate of loading of the ore increases with the relative energy consumption decrease, which is probably due to the fact that the mass of the ore does not affect the power of the mill on the one hand, and on the other - the addition of more ore also leads to more final product (higher relative productivity);
- as the mill filling increases, the relative energy consumption of the mill also increases because most of the energy is drawn to lift balls and large pieces of ore. This is an obvious conclusion, the mention of which is incorrect to omit.

The team believes that such a study should be repeated as the low energy consumption parameters are taken after the study of the relative indicators of the finished product and the study of the yield of the evaluated class. In this case, a comparison can be made by simultaneously achieving two or three target functions - high product quality and low energy consumption.

References

- Bojanov, E.S., Vuchkov, I.N., 1973. *Statisticheski metodi za modelirane i optimizirane na mnogofaktorni objekti*, Sofia, Tehnika.
- Bojanov, E.S., Vuchkov, I.N., 1979. *Statisticheski reshenia v proizvodstvoto I nauchnite izsledvania*. Sofia, Tehnika.
- Boteva, A., Vladkova, B., 2002. New selective collector for flotation of sulfide ores. *Annual of the University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski"*, 45, (2), 67–70.
- Dzhustrov, K., 2019. Influence of the ball load on the specific power consumption of ball mills. *Journal of mining and geological sciences*, 62, (3), 77–81.
- Hristova, T., 2015. Investigation of specific energy consumption in the SAG milling copper ores. *Annual of the University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski"*, 58, (3), 81–85.
- Hristova, T., Minin, I., Mitev, D., 2018. Determination of relative energy consumption of a jaw crusher in depending on the width of the discharge port and of the particle size distribution of the crushing product. *Journal of Mining and Geological science*, 61, (3), 13–17.
- Istalianov, R., Lakov, N., 2019. Energy control on the linings wear of semi-autogenous mills. *Journal of Mining and Geological science*, 62, (3), 104–106.
- Mryankov, I., Ivanov, A., 2007. *Izsledvane na prostranstvenite treptenya na vibratsionna melnitsa*. "Mehanika na machinite", 68, XV, (2), Izdatelstvo TU-Varna, 130–133.
- Nikolov, E., Nikolova, N., 2006. Analysis of energy losses in the valve of control system. - In Proc of IFAC ESC 2006 WS: Energy saving control in plants and buildings, October 2 - 5, 2006 Bansko, Bulgaria, 2006 IFAC, 135–140.
- Nikolova, N., Nikolov, E., 2006. Energy saving algorithms and control system, - In Proc of IFAC ESC 2006 WS: Energy saving control in plants and buildings, October 2 - 5, 2006 Bansko, Bulgaria, 2006 IFAC, 141–146.
- Nyandwe, E.M., Zhang, Q., Wang, D., 2020. Optimization of Ore Production in Copper Mine, *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 10, 61–74.
- Stoyanov, A., 2015. A task for the movement of a rigid body with the fixed point. *Annual of the University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski"*, 58, (3), 119–121. (in Bulgarian with English abstract)
- Uțu, I., Stochițoiu, M.D., Samoilă, L., Handra, A.D., 2020. Active power filters in order to limit the harmonic disturbance from electrical networks. *Annals of the University of Petrosani, Electrical Engineering*, 20 (2018).